

Self-Assembled Monolayer of N-Heterocyclic Carbene as a Primer in a Dual-Layer Coating for Corrosion Protection on Iron

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Abstract: The development of highly-stable coatings on iron is essential for mitigating corrosion formation. Herein, we demonstrate that a self-assembled monolayer of N-Heterocyclic Carbene (NHC) can be electrodeposited on iron foil and function as a binder for a secondary, crosslinked polymer network coating. The dual layer coating, constructed of a monolayer of NHCs and a polymer film, as a primary and a secondary coating, respectively, effectively prevented corrosion formation with a protective efficiency of $99.6 \pm 0.2\%$, as determined by polarization measurements in 3.5 wt% NaCl solution. Spectroscopic analysis identified the formation of a chemical interaction between the NHC monolayer and the polymer film. The strong anchoring of NHC to iron along with its chemical interaction with the polymer film induced high stability and durability of the dual layer coating to effectively protect the coated iron from corrosion formation.

The widespread use of iron in industry and manufacturing, along with its high susceptibility to corrosion, makes it essential to develop effective and sustainable strategies for corrosion mitigation on iron surfaces.^[1] One common approach involves the use of coatings to prevent the access of corrosive substances to the metal surface.^[2]

Methods for iron surface coating for corrosion mitigation include using inorganic or organic monolayers, primarily based on thiols and diazonium salts.^[3] However, monolayers on metal films, especially on iron, are characterized by limited chemical and thermal stability and provide inadequate long-term protection against environmental factors. For example, thiol-based monolayers suffer from oxidation and desorption, and degrade over time, especially under oxidative conditions, which limits their long-term protection efficiency.^[4] Diazonium salts, while initially effective, undergo hydrolysis and decomposition under acidic or basic conditions, compromising their protection functionality.^[5]

To further restrict the access of corrosive substances to iron surfaces, thin polymer films have been grafted either by using polymers with reactive end groups or by directly growing polymer chains from a pre-functionalized surface.^[6] The effectiveness of polymeric coatings towards corrosion mitigation has been

hindered by relatively poor adhesion and low surface density of the polymer on iron, leading to deteriorated stability under harsh conditions. Dual-layer coatings for improved corrosion mitigation have been prepared by attaching polymers to monolayers, mainly based on diazonium salt precursors that can be covalently attached to iron substrates.^[7] Nevertheless, the instability of such monolayers under environmental conditions deteriorate their adhesion strength and effectiveness as primers in dual-layer coatings.

The aforementioned limitations of current methods for iron coatings necessitate a new approach for corrosion mitigation. Herein, we demonstrate that the incorporation of N-Heterocyclic Carbene (NHC) self-assembled monolayer (SAM)^[8] as a primer in a dual-layer coating can induce a highly stable coating that effectively protects iron foils from corrosion formation. The high surface density and covalent anchoring of NHC-based SAMs to coinage metals have led to their utilization in various applications,^[9] including the use of polymer-NHC as surface ligands.^[10] It has been demonstrated that NHCs can also bind to metal-oxide surfaces and that NHC deposition can mitigate copper oxidation.^[11] The deposition of NHC-based SAMs on iron film was recently shown.^[12] However, the utilization of NHC monolayers on iron for corrosion mitigation have not yet been demonstrated.

NHC-based SAM was employed herein as a chemical binder between an iron foil and a polymer film, demonstrating its effectiveness as an adhesion promoter in a dual-layer coating. The integration of NHC monolayer and polymer film, as a primary and a secondary coating layers, respectively, provided a highly effective dual-layer protection that prevented corrosion formation on iron under harsh conditions.

1,3-dimethylbenzimidazolyliidene (benzNHC) was self-assembled on an iron foil by electrodeposition,^[13] using 0.1 M of tetraethylammonium tetrafluoroborate (TEATFB) as a supporting electrolyte and 5 mM of triple-distilled water (Scheme 1). In this process, deprotonation of 1,3-dimethyl-1H-benzimidazolium iodide (DMBI) into benzNHC was induced via its exposure to hydroxide ions, which were formed near an iron electrode by electrochemical water reduction reaction (see SI for experimental details).^[13a, 14]

Scheme 1. Dual layer coating formation on iron foil

In the second step of the coating process, the benzNHC-coated iron foil was spin-coated with bisphenol-A ethoxylate diacrylate (BPA-EDA) monomers mixed with diphenyl(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)phosphine oxide (TPO) photoinitiator. Crosslinked polymer network (CPN) was prepared by photopolymerization of BPA-EDA.^[6c] In this process, TPO functions as a photo-initiator for a radical polymerization reaction, leading to the formation of a three-dimensional crosslinked network (see SI for experimental details). Spectroscopic analysis of the benzNHC monolayer properties and its interaction with the CPN will be discussed in detail below.

The evaluation of anti-corrosive efficacy typically employs potentiodynamic polarization measurements in a saline environment, with 3.5 wt% NaCl solution being a common choice.^[15] This simulates a harsh corrosive environment where the anodic reaction involves iron oxidation to iron ions, and the cathodic reaction includes the reduction of water and oxygen.^[16] The presence of Cl^- ions further exacerbate the corrosion process by strongly adsorbing to the metal surface and accelerating the formation of corrosive intermediates.^[16-17] In the current work, we analyzed the effectiveness of the benzNHC-CPN dual layer coating in a saline environment to ensure a direct and meaningful evaluation of its corrosion mitigation effectiveness.

Polymer-coated iron samples were extracted using Focused Ion Beam (FIB) to identify the polymer film thickness and its stability following exposure to saline environment. Iridium was deposited on the polymer film to protect it during the milling process. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) imaging identified a film thickness of 11.8 and 6.6 μm for the CPN film with and without the benzNHC monolayer, respectively (Figure 1a and 1b). It is hypothesized that the high surface density of benzNHC, which function as active sites for on-surface polymerization, as will be discussed below, enabled the formation of a thicker film on the metal surface, in comparison to the film that was prepared on the bare iron foil.

Figure 1. FIB-SEM analysis of polymer-coated iron foils before (a-b) and after (c-d) their immersion in NaCl solution and exposure to potentiodynamic polarization measurements. The iron foils were coated with a crosslinked polymer network (CPN) with (a and c) and without (b and d) benzNHC monolayer as a binder. A protective layer of Iridium (Ir) was deposited on the polymer prior to FIB extraction.

Potentiodynamic polarization measurements were employed to evaluate the anti-corrosive efficacy of the developed dual-layer coatings. Figure 2 presents Tafel plots of four distinct samples: bare iron foil, CPN- and benzNHC-coated iron foil, and a sample with a dual-layer coating that includes benzNHC and CPN, as a primer and a secondary coating, respectively. The potentiodynamic polarization measurements were conducted in a 3.5 wt% NaCl solution maintained at 25 °C, simulating a saline corrosive environment.

Figure 2. Potentiodynamic polarization curves of a bare iron foil (green-colored curve), CPN-coated iron foil (red-colored curve), benzNHC-coated iron foil (blue-colored curve) and an iron foil that was coated with a dual layer (CPN on benzNHC) coating (black-colored curve). All samples were immersed in 3.5 wt% NaCl solution at 25 °C.

Figure 2 shows that iron foil with benzNHC monolayer coating exhibits a corrosion current density (i_{corr}) that is similar to that of the bare iron ($i_{\text{corr}} = 0.35 \pm 0.03$ and $0.32 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ for the bare and benzNHC coated iron foil, respectively). The measured i_{corr} values for bare iron are comparable to previously published data in NaCl solutions.^[18] BenzNHC monolayer coatings slightly reduced the corrosion potential ($E_{\text{corr}} = -644$ mV) compared to the bare iron foil ($E_{\text{corr}} = -701$ mV) indicating that the coating increased the threshold at which corrosion is initiated. CPN films were less effective in corrosion protection than the benzNHC monolayer, with $E_{\text{corr}} = -706$ mV, which is similar to the bare iron foils and demonstrates the weak adhesion of CPN films to iron.

Conversely, iron foils that were coated with a dual layer of benzNHC and CPN demonstrated a substantial decrease in both anodic and cathodic currents, indicative of a more effective barrier against both cathodic and anodic reactions. This is quantitatively confirmed by a significant reduction of more than two orders of magnitude in corrosion currents ($i_{\text{corr}} = 0.0012 \pm 0.0003 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$), in comparison to the bare iron foil. In addition, the Tafel plots exhibit a notable shift towards more noble corrosion potentials ($E_{\text{corr}} = -226$ mV) for the dual layer coated sample.

The protective efficiency, P_i , of the coating was determined from the polarization curves by

$$P_i(\%) = 100 \left(1 - \frac{i_{\text{cor}}}{i_{\text{cor}}^0} \right)$$

where i_{cor} and i_{cor}^0 denote the average corrosion current densities in the presence and absence of the coating, respectively (Figure S1).^[19] The values of P_i for the dual-layer coated iron foil was 99.6 ± 0.2 %. These results suggest that the CPN film, once polymerized on the benzNHC monolayer, forms a robust protective barrier, substantially limiting the metal's exposure to corrosion. Furthermore, prolonged immersion tests demonstrated that the dual-layer coating induced low corrosion currents over an extended time duration of up to 24 hours (Figure

S2). These results emphasize the enhanced efficacy and stability of the dual-layer coating, ensuring durable and reliable corrosion resistance over time. Changes in the electrolyte composition, such as varying the types of anions or adjusting the pH, have the potential to further improve the coating protection efficiency in other, more specific environments.

FIB-SEM measurements of the polymer-coated samples were conducted following their exposure to potentiodynamic polarization measurements. SEM measurements identified a polymer thickness of 6.7 μm for the dual-coated iron foil (Figure 1c), while a detachment of the polymer film was detected for the sample in which the polymer was directly deposited on the bare iron foil (Figure 1d). Exposure of the dual layer coating to NaCl solution led to film shrinkage, correlated to ion-polymer interactions.^[20] The obtained results reveal the crucial role of benzNHC monolayer as a binder of the polymer film to the iron foil. NHC monolayer was found essential for the formation of a polymer film that is strongly anchored to the iron foil.

Spectroscopic measurements were conducted to identify the chemical properties of benzNHC and its interaction with the polymer film (Figure 3). N1s X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were conducted to assess the chemisorption and self-assembly of benzNHC on Fe foil (Figure 3a, black-colored spectrum). N1s XPS peak was identified at 399.7 eV, and the XPS signal was constructed of two Gaussians. The dominant Gaussian was centered at 399.6 eV, correlated to chemisorbed benzNHC, and was similar in its position to NHCs that were chemisorbed on Fe and Cu films.^[11c, 12] A minor Gaussian was centered at 401.0 eV and was correlated to nitrogen background signature that originated from nitrogen contamination in the iron foil (Figure S3). It cannot be excluded that some contribution to the high binding energy signal is due to the presence of a pyrrolic species,^[9i, 21] commonly observed after partial decomposition of the imidazole ring. Fe2p XPS analysis showed an overall increase in the XPS signal correlated to the self-cleaning nature of NHC deposition, without noticeable changes in the oxidation state of Fe (Figure S4).

Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) measurements of benzNHC on iron were conducted (Figure 3b, black-colored spectrum) following a recently developed protocol for NHC monolayer probing on surfaces.^[22] A detailed analysis of Raman mode assignments is included in Table S1. Diagnostic Raman signals were detected at 1370 cm^{-1} , correlated to CC stretch, CN stretch, CH bending and indicative of a vertical configuration of benzNHC, based on previously-reported normal mode analysis.^[22b] Bands at 795, 1010, and 1183 cm^{-1} , correlated to aromatic CH wagging, ring-breathing and in-plane aromatic CH bending, respectively (Table S1),^[23] and corroborate the population of flat-lying molecules, as recently identified by experimental and theoretical normal modes analysis.^[22b] The overall Raman pattern was similar to that of benzNHC on Au surfaces (Figure S5),^[22b, 24] thus indicating that most of the benzNHCs were chemisorbed on iron without fragmentation or chemical deformation. SERS measurements further revealed the electrochemical stability of benzNHC on Fe surface in a voltage window of -0.3 to 0.5 V vs. Ag/AgCl. (Figure S6).^[24]

Figure 3. N1s XPS (a) and SERS (b) signals of iron foil that was coated with benzNHC monolayer. Measurements were acquired before and after exposure of the supported benzNHC monolayer to TPO and methyl acrylate and their illumination (black- and red-colored spectra, respectively).

Spectroscopic measurements were conducted to elucidate the mechanism by which benzNHC functions as a chemical binder to the CPN film. In these experiments, methyl-acrylate was used as a monomer homolog in order to study the interaction between NHC and BPA-EDA, without masking the NHC signal due to polymer film growth.

N1s XPS signal was acquired following exposure of the chemisorbed benzNHC to methyl acrylate (with 0.1% TPO and following illumination; see SI for additional information). A single dominant feature was detected at 399.7 eV (Figure 3a, red-colored spectrum). The decrease in the overall amplitude of the N1s XPS signal was correlated to the presence of methyl acrylate, supported by the overall increase in the C1s XPS signal (Figure S7). A more noticeable decrease was identified in the high binding-energy component in the N1s XPS feature, in comparison to the lower binding energy component. This provides another indication that the high binding-energy feature originates from deeper layers of nitrogen contamination, which are located in the iron foil.

The exposure to methyl acrylate led to dominant changes in the SERS spectra (Figure 3b, red-colored spectrum, see table S1 for vibrational assignments). Significantly, peaks at 840 and 1580 cm^{-1} , correlated to C-O-C vibration and C-C stretch, respectively,

along with a broad shoulder at 1730 cm⁻¹, correlated to C=O vibration, were probed and correlated to the chemical signature of methyl ester.^[25] SERS signal at 997 cm⁻¹ along with the lack of a signal at 1373 cm⁻¹, which is indicative of a vertical orientation, can potentially indicate a favorable flat-lying benzNHC signature.^[22b] SERS measurements uncovered changes in the structure and orientation of benzNHC already after exposure to TPO and illumination, prior to exposure to methyl-acrylate, demonstrating the role of TPO in inducing chemical interaction between the surface-anchored NHC and methyl acrylate (Figure S8).^[26] The spectroscopic measurements also demonstrate the stability of surface-anchored benzNHC, with no indication for desorption during the photo-induced reaction.^[22]

The similarity in the SERS spectra of benzNHC on Fe and Au foils, both before and after exposure to TPO and methyl acrylate (Figure 3b and Figure S5), indicate that similar chemical changes in the benzNHC monolayer are induced on both surfaces. Based on this spectroscopic similarity, laser desorption ionization mass-spectrometry (LDI-MS) measurements were conducted on Au film to identify the chemical reactivity of benzNHC after exposure to TPO and methyl acrylate under illumination (Figure S9). Following benzNHC deposition, LDI-MS signal was detected at 147.1 m/z, and correlated to (benzNHC-H)⁺.^[27] This signature was not probed after exposure to methyl acrylate and TPO, while a new signature was probed at 219.1 m/z and was correlated to the formation of methyl-ester tethered benzNHC. These results can indicate that methyl ester tethered benzNHC via N-methyl bond activation.

In order to further assess the chemical role of the imidazole ring in polymer film stabilization, we have tested the efficiency of NHC (dimethyl-imidazolylidene) SAM as a primer in a dual layer coating for corrosion mitigation. The chemical difference between the benzNHC and NHC is in the lack of the benzyl ring. This comparative analysis therefore provides information about the role of the benzyl ring in surface-anchoring of NHC and its functionality as a chemical binder for the polymer film.

Tafel measurements identified that NHC SAM can function as well as a primer coating to mitigate corrosion formation on iron foil (Figure S10), though at lower effectiveness than that of benzNHC SAM. These results demonstrate that surface anchoring and chemical coordination of the polymer film with the SAM are initiated via interaction with the imidazolylidene ring, while the role of the benzylic group is to stabilize the surface anchored NHCs by intermolecular interactions.^[28]

To conclude, in this work we show that a benzNHC monolayer can be self-assembled on iron foil and functions as a binder for a secondary coating of a cross-linked polymer network. The dual-layer coating, constructed of benzNHC monolayer and CPN film as a primer and a secondary coating, respectively, functions as an effective blocking layer and showed high efficiency in mitigating corrosion formation on iron foils.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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N-Heterocyclic Carbene (NHC) monolayer was electrodeposited on Fe foil and effectively functioned as a binder for a secondary layer of a cross-linked polymer network, which was photo-polymerized on the NHC monolayer. The dual coating, constructed of NHC monolayer and polymer film, as a primary and a secondary coating, respectively, effectively prevented corrosion formation on Fe.